

MÉTODOS PARA ENDURECIMENTO E MELHORIA DAS CARACTERÍSTICAS DE FADIGA DE AMOSTRAS DE LIGAS DE NÍQUEL CROMO-FERRO E TITÂNIO**METHODS FOR HARDENING AND IMPROVEMENT OF FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS OF TITANIUM AND IRON-CHROMIUM NICKEL ALLOY SAMPLES****МЕТОДЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОЧНОСТИ И УСТАЛОСТНЫХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК ОБРАЗЦОВ, ИЗГОТОВЛЕННЫХ ИЗ СПЛАВОВ ТИТАНА И ЖЕЛЕЗОХРОМОНИКЕЛЕВЫХ СПЛАВОВ**

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RESUMO

Este trabalho descreve o procedimento para determinar tensões residuais na superfície usando o método mecânico e quatro métodos de endurecimento de amostras. A urgência do problema declarado no artigo se deve ao fato de que as tensões de tração superficial que surgem na fabricação de peças altamente carregadas podem reduzir significativamente as características mecânicas, de recursos e de fadiga dos produtos. O objetivo do estudo foi endurecer amostras de ligas de titânio e ferro-cromo-níquel para melhorar suas características de resistência, fadiga, recursos e determinar tensões residuais por remoção camada por camada das camadas estudadas por ataque eletroquímico. A determinação das tensões residuais da superfície foi realizada mecanicamente, utilizando um complexo de medição e cálculo durante a gravação contínua do metal a partir da superfície de teste da amostra, o que possibilitou medir as tensões residuais em diferentes profundidades e determinar a energia do estado de estresse da superfície. As tensões residuais foram calculadas a partir da deformação da parte restante da amostra com uma mudança na profundidade das camadas estudadas. O endurecimento das amostras foi realizado de quatro maneiras, a saber: endurecimento por ultrassom; cura por ultrassom + Rosler (processamento de vibração); Rosler (processamento de vibração) + cura por ultrassom; Rosler (processamento de vibração) + endurecimento por ultrassom. Os resultados do estudo mostraram que a superfície dos produtos é uma área mais fraca que a interna. Após a têmpera, surgem tensões compressivas na superfície de todas as amostras de ligas de titânio e ferro-cromo-níquel. O caso preferido de endurecimento é o segundo (endurecimento ultrassônico + endurecimento centrífugo). A presença de tensões compressivas residuais nas camadas externas dos produtos aumenta seu limite de fadiga em $\pm 20\%$. Os resultados do trabalho podem ser usados para fabricar produtos com altas características mecânicas, de recursos e de fadiga.

Palavras-chave: *tensões residuais, ultrassom, deformação, resistência, macro estresses.*

ABSTRACT

This work describes the procedure for determining residual surface stresses using the mechanical method and four methods of hardening samples. The urgency of the problem stated in the article is due to the fact that surface tensile stresses arising in the manufacture of highly loaded parts can significantly reduce the mechanical, resource and fatigue characteristics of products. The aim of the study was to harden samples of titanium and iron-chromium-nickel alloys to improve their strength, fatigue and resource characteristics and determine residual stresses by layer-by-layer removal of the studied layers by electrochemical etching. The determination of surface residual stresses was carried out mechanically using a measuring and calculation complex during continuous etching of the metal from the test surface of the sample, which made it possible to measure the residual stresses at different depths and determine the energy of the surface stress state. Residual stresses were calculated from the deformation of the remaining part of the sample with a change in the depth of the studied layers. The hardening of the samples was carried out in four ways, namely: ultrasonic hardening; ultrasonic curing + Rosler (vibration

processing); Rosler (vibration processing) + ultrasonic curing; Rosler (vibration processing) + ultrasonic hardening. The results of the study showed that the surface of the products is a weaker area than the inside. After quenching, surface compressive stresses arise for all samples of titanium and iron-chromium-nickel alloys. The preferred case of hardening is the second (ultrasonic hardening + centrifugal hardening). The presence of residual compressive stresses in the outer layers of the products increases their fatigue limit by $\approx 20\%$. The results of the work can be used to manufacture products with high mechanical, resource and fatigue characteristics.

Keywords: *residual stresses, ultrasound, deformation, strength, macrostresses.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной работе описана процедура определения остаточных поверхностных напряжений с использованием механического метода и четырех способов упрочнения образцов. Актуальность заявленной в статье проблемы обусловлена тем, что поверхностные растягивающие напряжения, возникающие при изготовлении высоконагруженных деталей, могут существенно снизить механические, ресурсные и усталостные характеристики изделий. Целью исследования является закалка образцов из титановых и железо-хромоникелевых сплавов для улучшения их прочностных, усталостных и ресурсных характеристик и определения остаточных напряжений путем послойного снятия исследуемых слоев методом электрохимического травления. Определение поверхностных остаточных напряжений проводилось механическим методом с использованием измерительно-расчетного комплекса при непрерывном травлении металла с исследуемой поверхности образца, что позволило измерить остаточные напряжения на разных глубинах залегания и определить энергию напряженного состояния поверхности. Остаточные напряжения рассчитывались по деформации оставшейся части образца с изменением глубины залегания исследуемых слоев. Упрочнение образцов было проведено четырьмя способами, а именно: ультразвуковое упрочнение; ультразвуковое отверждение + рослер (виброобработка); Рослер (виброобработка) + ультразвуковое отверждение; Рослер (виброобработка) + ультразвуковое упрочнение. Результаты исследования показали, что поверхность изделий является более слабой областью, чем внутренняя часть. После закалки возникают поверхностные сжимающие напряжения для всех образцов из титана и железо-хромоникелевых сплавов. Предпочтительным случаем упрочнения является второй (ультразвуковое упрочнение + центробежное упрочнение). Наличие остаточных сжимающих напряжений во внешних слоях изделий увеличивает предел их усталости на $\approx 20\%$. Результаты работы могут быть использованы для изготовления изделий с высокими механическими, ресурсными и усталостными характеристиками.

Ключевые слова: *остаточные напряжения, ультразвук, деформация, прочность, макронапряжения.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

When producing high-loaded details, one of the problems is the presence of surface tensile stresses (Gnyusov *et al.*, 2017; Hou *et al.*, 2018). They can substantially reduce the mechanical, resource, and fatigue characteristics of products (Wojtaszek *et al.*, 2016; Sakhvadze *et al.*, 2017; Pei & Duan, 2017; Huang *et al.*, 2018). The residual stresses exist in products in the absence of external actions. Three types of stresses are distinguished: macro stresses, micro stresses, and elastic stresses (Birger, 1963; Colegrove *et al.*, 2013; Hamad & Hassan, 2018; Astapov *et al.*, 2019a; Astapov *et al.*, 2019b; Cui *et al.*, 2020; Su *et al.*, 2020).

The main methods to determine residual stresses are mechanical and x-ray methods (Liu *et al.*, 2019; Sunder, 2016; Mohanty & Muduli, 2020). The mechanical process is most widely spread because it uses the same concepts of stresses and deformations of elastic body mechanics as those used when calculating the strength, rigidity,

and stability of details. The mechanical method of determination of residual stresses is based on cutting a sample from detail and subsequent layer-by-layer removal of the layers under investigation using electrochemical etching (Antolovich & Armstrong, 2014; Mustafin, 2006; Samarin *et al.*, 2019; Makarenko & Kuznetsova, 2019; Ding *et al.*, 2015).

The object of the work was to harden samples made of titanium and iron-chromium-nickel alloys for improvement of their strength, fatigue, and resource characteristics and determination of residual stresses by layer-by-layer removal of the studied layers using electrochemical etching.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The determination of residual surface stresses was made by the mechanical method using a measuring-calculating complex at the continuous etching of metal from the sample surface under investigation (Figure 1). Such a

plant measures residual stresses at different occurrence depths and determines the energy of surface stressed state, as well as makes it possible to optimize and control the stability of technological processes (Figure 2).

An experiment began by cutting a sample of standard sizes 50x4x2 mm (Figure 3). Then the sample was fastened into a holder (investigated face down); the holder and surface that was not subjected to etching were coated with paraffin. A steel ball was fastened in paraffin at the sample upper surface where deformation was measured (for contact with an inductive transducer). Then the holder with the sample was suspended to a carriage of the gage post, and the steel ball was brought to the inductive transducer to the point of maximal contacting. After this, the carriage was put into the electrolyte, and the etching process began. The balance became disturbed, causing the sample to deform. The residual stresses σ were calculated from the deformation of the remaining part of the sample, with changing occurrence depth of the layers studied (Birger, 1963; Gnatyuk, 2017; Lu *et al.*, 2018; Madzivhandila *et al.*, 2019).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. Determination of residual stresses

Let us consider the determination of axial residual stresses in a prismatic rod. We assume that, except for small areas at the ends of the rod, the residual stresses are constant along its length. To determine the residual stresses, we will sequentially remove the ABCD layers of materials (Figure 4) located in the zone of constant (along the length) stresses. The end sections are not removed; they are placed in the grips of the device.

The residual stresses σ in the surface layers of the initial detail were determined as a sum of stresses relaxed because of sample cutting from the detail (σ_d) and a nonlinear component ($\sigma_{n.l.}$) due to removal of layers from the sample surface (Equation 1). Depending on the sample thickness and value of mechanical stresses in the layers under investigation, layers separation from the detail may lead to its bending F_b and (or) change of its length ε_b . In this case, the variation of the initial stresses may be calculated as a linear component from their occurrence depth (Equation 2). Here E is the material modulus of elasticity; F_b is the bending because of sample cutting from the detail; K_0 and K_1 are the coefficients representing both form and sizes of the sample; K_{amp} is the

deformation amplification coefficient at different ways of fastening the sample and transducer in the process of cutting; ε_b is sample's relative extension at cutting.

Let us determine the residual stresses $\sigma_{n.l.}$ acting in the rod at a distance a from the upper face of the rod (Figure 4). As a result of the removal of a layer of material with a thickness a , the remaining part of the rod is deformed under the action of stresses along the planes AB and DC.

Let stresses $\sigma_{n.l.}(a)$ act at a distance ξ from the upper face. The bending moment M from stresses on the face AB relative to the middle of the rod height (point O) is (Equation 3), where b is the width of the rod. If the rod is bent by the concentrated moments M at the end, then the deflection is (Equation 4), where l , h is the length and thickness of the rod, respectively, J is the moment of inertia of the cross-section (Equation 5). Neglecting the influence of axial forces on bending and taking into account (Equation 4) and (Equation 5), we find (Equation 6). Transferring the value $(h-a)^3$ to the left side of the equality and differentiating the integral over the upper limit a , we obtain (Equation 7). From (Equation 7) at $a=0$ we obtain the formula for determining the residual stresses in the outer layer (Equation 8). After differentiating equality (Equation 7) with respect to a , we have (Equation 9). Integrating both sides of this equality, we obtain (Equation 10).

Given the relation (Equation 8), we can obtain the equation (Equation 11). The residual stresses varying with occurrence depth of the removing layers were calculated from the expression that takes into account not only the measured deformation for each current depth but also those residual deformations that relaxed due to the removal of the previous layers. The residual stresses component that varies with etching depth was calculated for prismatic samples in real time scale (Equation 11). Here L_{et} is the etched layer length; H is the sample thickness; F is the current value of sample deformation; $\frac{dF}{da}$ is deformation variation with occurrence depth of the layers under investigation; a_i is the current depth of removed layers; ξ is the total current deformation.

When determining the residual stresses, the balance of forces over the sample thickness is violated because of etching of the layers studied that are in the stress state, and the sample bends. The stresses in the layer under investigation are calculated from that bending (deformation). In this

case, the balance of forces is restored, and partial relaxation of stress state occurs on the opposite side of the sample, in accordance with the bending moment (Sangid, 2013; Ahmad *et al.*, 2018; Aguilera-Correa *et al.*, 2019). Due to the specially chosen etching conditions, an exact calculation of the depth of etched layers is done from the amount of passed electric current according to Faraday's law (Equation 12).

Here a is the etched layer depth; t is the etching time; I is current in the etching series; α is the effective electrochemical equivalent; ρ is the sample material density; B is the sample width. Shown in Figures 5 and 6 are the samples of titanium and iron-chromium-nickel alloys after etching. Figures 7 and 8 present the diagrams of surface residual stresses distribution in the samples of titanium (Li *et al.*, 2016; Kumar *et al.*, 2017; Kim *et al.*, 2013) and iron-chromium-nickel alloys (Jiang & Zhao, 2012; Debroy *et al.*, 2018). One can see that surface tensile stresses are present on samples of both types. The presence of such stresses (from 50 MPa and more) considerably reduces vibration and fatigue strength of the product (Malaki & Ding, 2015; Zhu *et al.*, 2017; Lin *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2020).

To solve the above problem, hardening of samples was performed in four ways: 1 – ultrasonic hardening; 2 – ultrasonic hardening + Rosler (vibratory finishing); 3 – Rosler (vibratory finishing) + ultrasonic hardening; 4 – Rosler (vibratory finishing) + ultrasonic hardening (He *et al.*, 2018; Sangid, 2013). In all four cases, the parameters of ultrasonic hardening remained unchanged: amplitude of 100 μm and rated frequency of 20 kHz.

3.2. Centrifugal Hardening (Rosler)

Centrifugal treatment (Figure 9) is a high-performance method for finishing and hardening parts. The method of volumetric centrifugal treatment consists in the fact that the granular processing medium with the details is rotationally driven around the vertical axis so that it takes on the shape of a torus in which particles move along spiral paths. The machined parts are loaded into the working chamber and moved together with the working environment. Hardening is carried out due to the relative movement and interaction of the granular medium and the parts wetted by a liquid continuously supplied to the working chamber.

3.3. Ultrasonic hardening

The strain hardening of the surface layer of samples during ultrasonic hardening (Figure 10) is

carried out due to the kinetic energy of steel balls randomly moving in a spatially limited volume. The surface treatment takes place in the "cloud" of the working medium (balls) simultaneously from two sides. This type of treatment causes an increase in hardness of the surface layer by 18% and an increase in surface compressive stresses to 1000 MPa. The depth of the riveted layer is 20-25 μm . Structural changes in the surface zones of the part cause an increase in the durability of products up to 1.5 times at cyclic stresses of 1650-2600 MPa. After hardening of samples in four ways, residual surface stresses were measured, and the diagrams of their distribution were obtained (Furuya, 2013; Kim *et al.*, 2016; Cai *et al.*, 2017; Zhan *et al.*, 2018; Su *et al.*, 2018; Klimenko *et al.*, 2018; Qiao *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2020). The results of the measurements are presented in Figures 11 and 12.

One can see from figures that after hardening, there are surface compressive stresses for all samples made of titanium and iron-chromium-nickel alloys. The preferred case of hardening is the second (ultrasonic hardening + centrifugal hardening). In this case, the maximum compressive residual stresses reach 550 MPa at a depth of 50 μm . The presence of residual compressive stresses in the outer layers of products increases their fatigue limit by $\approx 20\%$.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The results of the investigations showed that the surface of products studied is a "weaker" area than the interior. Therefore, any process that leads to appearance and increase of surface compressive stresses will be positive for material operation. After quenching, surface compressive stresses arise for all samples of titanium and iron-chromium-nickel alloys. The preferred case of hardening is the second (ultrasonic hardening + centrifugal hardening). The presence of residual compressive stresses in the outer layers of the products increases their fatigue limit by $\approx 20\%$. The results of the work can be used to manufacture products with high mechanical, resource and fatigue characteristics.

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$$\sigma = \sigma_d + \sigma_{n.l.} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$\sigma_d = E \left\{ \left[\frac{K_1}{K_{amp}} \right] \cdot F_b - K_0 \cdot \varepsilon_b \right\} n \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$M = \int_0^a \sigma_{n.l.}(\xi) \left(\frac{1}{2}(h-a) - \xi \right) b d\xi \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$f = \frac{Ml^2}{8EJ} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

$$J = \frac{b(h-a)^3}{12} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

$$F(a) = \frac{3l^2}{2E(h-a)^3} \cdot \int_0^a \sigma_{n.l.}(\xi) \left[\frac{1}{2}(h+a) - \xi \right] b d\xi \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

$$(h-a)^2 \frac{dF}{da}(a) - 3(h-a)^2 F(a) = \frac{3l^2}{2E} \left[\frac{1}{2} \int_0^a \sigma_{n.l.}(\xi) d\xi + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{n.l.}(a)(h-a) \right] \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

$$\sigma_{n.l.}(0) = \frac{4Eh^2}{3l^2} \frac{dF}{da}(0) \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

$$(h-a)^2 \frac{d^2 F(a)}{da^2} - 6(h-a) \frac{dF(a)}{da} + 6F(a) = \frac{3l^2}{4E} \frac{d\sigma_{n.l.}(a)}{da} \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

$$(h-a)^2 \frac{dF(a)}{da} - 4(h-a)F(a) + 2 \int_0^a F(\xi) d\xi - h^2 \frac{dF(0)}{da} = \frac{3l^2}{4E} [\sigma_{n.l.}(a) - \sigma_{n.l.}(0)] \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

$$\sigma_{n.l.} = \left(\frac{4E}{3L_{et}^2 K_{amp}} \right) \cdot \left[(H-a_i)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{dF}{da} \right) - 4(H-a_i)F_{a_i} + 2 \int_0^{a_i} F(\xi) d\xi \right] \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

$$a = \frac{\alpha \cdot t \cdot \int_0^i Idt}{\rho \cdot L_{et} \cdot B} \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

Figure 1. Photo of the surface of titanium samples after machining (magnification 100×)

Figure 2. Installation diagram: the electric current source IL-02 delivers electric current to a bath with electrolyte; BIN 2 measures sample deformation

Figure 3. The scheme of cutting samples for determining residual stresses

Figure 4. The geometry of the rod when etching layers and emerging mechanical stresses

Figure 5. Sample of the titanium alloy after etching

Figure 6. Sample of the iron-chromium-nickel alloy after etching

Figure 7. Diagram of residual stresses distribution in a sample of titanium alloy before hardening

Figure 8. Diagram of residual stresses distribution in a sample of iron-chromium-nickel alloy before hardening

Figure 9. Installation for centrifugal hardening treatment (Rosler)

Figure 10. Installation for ultrasonic hardening

Figure 11. Diagram of residual stresses distribution in samples of titanium alloy after hardening

Figure 12. Diagram of residual stresses distribution in samples of iron-chromium-nickel alloy after hardening